

THE ORETICAL PRINCIPLES OF DEVELOPMENT OF STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT COMPETENCE OF LEADING PERSONNEL BASED ON INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract. *Emphasizing the criteria for forming the leader's personal training, we mean initiative: energy, cheerfulness, risk-taking, self-activity in obtaining information, independence, the ability to make one's choice based on humane principles rather than being influenced by the situation. ; under orientation: general orientation to success, constant renewal and improvement of physical, intellectual, emotional and spiritual potentials, striving for a harmonious balance of these possibilities, plans for the future; under autonomy: high reflection of oneself and the surrounding world, transition from external determination of one's own behavior to self-determination of one's own destiny, uniformity of professional privileges for a long time, assumption of responsibility.*

Keywords: *personal training, educational problems, repertoire networks, cognitive, ontological.*

Emphasizing the criteria for forming the leader's personal training, we mean initiative: energy, cheerfulness, risk-taking, self-activity in obtaining information, independence, the ability to make one's choice based on humane principles rather than being influenced by the situation. ; under orientation: general orientation to success, constant renewal and improvement of physical, intellectual, emotional and spiritual potentials, striving for a harmonious balance of these possibilities, plans for the future; under autonomy: high reflection of oneself and the surrounding world, transition from external determination of one's own behavior to self-determination of one's own destiny, uniformity of professional privileges for a long time, assumption of responsibility .

To determine the level of personal readiness of the leader, we used the principle of active, autonomous and directed adaptation of the person to the environment. The higher the level of personal regulation (we distinguish three of them), the more effective it is to form a state of personal readiness (adaptation) to life conditions. Thus, the selective level is characterized by an underestimated level of personal regulation, that is, an active, focused, autonomous adaptation to the environment and a reluctance to implement innovative activities. The quasi-stationary level is characterized by partial or satisfactory adaptation, but here the success of adaptation is still dependent on the external conditions of the environment, the familiarity of situations, i.e. lack of readiness for active, directed and autonomous adaptation to the environment and implementation of innovative activities. Integrative-synergistic level: a person at this level easily adapts to new life conditions, is very operative and adequately oriented in situations, quickly develops a strategy for his behavior and socialization, meaningfully connects conflicting life events, all finds patterns in events. able to increase the strengths of life and compensate for the weaknesses, has a positive winning spirit.[1]

The process of realizing a person's innovative potential and personal preparation of a leader can be expressed as a unity of three potential opportunities that are updated in the process of

interaction to perceive new information, adequately evaluate a new phenomenon and change it. and readiness for effective innovative activity. The characteristics of this interaction determine the ratio of leadership types to the actualization of innovative opportunities and can be the basis for determining the types of leaders and their management styles. Assessment of the quality of achieving the target innovative function and management competence is achieved by determining the preference for one or another type and method of management (according to the principle of efficiency) in a specific problem situation.[2]

In practice, it is studied by dividing the leaders into the following groups to improve their skills.

Type A - conservative - focuses on familiar, repeatedly proven ways of working. He misbehaves with the new, ridicules, rejects the proposals of subordinates, has low autonomy, when given instructions from above, he tries to transfer the implementation work to deputies or extend the deadlines. In the management of such leaders, the initiative of actions is very patterned, rigid, patterned. Motivation for success and the need for self-actualization are weakly expressed. Innovation potential is low. The low innovation potential of the manager causes an authoritarian style of management, strict control over performance and official recognition of his powers. Such leaders strive for high positions for personal prestige, they act with the fear of failure rather than the desire for success. The effectiveness of introducing innovations into the educational process is close to 50%.

Type B - avant-garde - constantly focuses on new, more economical and appropriate ways to achieve organizational goals; developed a new, advanced sense; thinks independently regardless of who the proposals are put forward by; carefully considers all options; reasonable risk taking. Activity in introducing innovations to the educational process. Innovation potential is average or high. Managers with high innovative potential are distinguished by the following characteristics: the ability to cover the whole while paying attention to details, the ability to quickly find non-standard solutions, the ability to foresee social and legal consequences, the pursuit of success and the fear of failure, not the risk. ability to do. Due to the practical orientation of thinking, the leader-innovator quickly understands the problem, evaluates the prospects of innovation and takes decisive measures to implement them. High innovative potential is provided by a developed system of delegation of authority, involving employees in the decision-making process, and in relation to long-term tasks.

Type V - a demonstrator - aims to maintain the image of a democratic, progressive, proactive manager, in words and even in front of the public - for any innovation, but in reality - includes only those who do not require a large amount of work. , energy and risk; autonomy is weak, focused on the perspective of higher authority; initiative in implementing innovations is low, lack of professional skills, often changes their attitude to innovations due to self-doubt. Innovation potential is average or below average. The psychological climate in the institution is determined by the "mood to solve current problems within the framework of one's workplace."

Type G - the rebuilders - is constantly focused on various and unreasonable changes; restructuring is the mania of such a leader. Autonomous, but his thinking is abstract and formal, active in actions, but does not bother with deep preliminary analysis and reasoning, innovates by trial and error. First of all, he tries to change the organizational structure, and when this opportunity ends, he begins to "shuffle" the management staff. The innovative potential of such leaders is often average

Modern educational problems encourage the search for new management tools that can identify not only old, but also newly emerging problems in modern social conditions, which leads to the search for new approaches, forms, tools and methods of training new types of personnel. head of the education system. The task of forming a forward-looking, innovative type of leader - a manager with innovative and management skills - becomes urgent. This concept still does not have its place and clear definition in domestic and foreign publications compared to concepts such as competence, competence, management competence, innovative competence, which we will not consider in this article, but more we pay attention. The essence and structure of the new category that we are promoting. "Innovative and management competence". There is no methodological base that reveals the content of the concept of "innovative and management competence of a person", its structure and implementation mechanisms, its purpose, the system of interactions and relationships. Methods of diagnosis and development of innovative and management competence in the science of psychology and pedagogy, methods of its research identifies a lack of ideas about provision. During our theoretical research, we set ourselves the task of studying the dynamic, multifaceted process of innovative interaction of a person with the world. And, first of all, they believed that it is necessary to determine the methodological directions for the formation of a person-oriented theory of the management of innovative processes in the educational system.[3]

At the same time, psychological-pedagogical research does not fully cover the issues related to the study and development of innovative activities in the educational system. There are objective difficulties in the introduction of innovative technologies in the field of modern education. In general, in the context of the development of innovative processes, the reform of modern education is determined by the need to solve existing problems: neglecting the individual characteristics of the subject of activity; use of ineffective traditional forms and methods of education and training; widening the gap between education and training; aggravation of the problem of humanization of formal and informal relations in the educational process; the gap between societal demands, educational opportunities and individual needs. In addition, research shows that indiscriminate (not based on scientific learning) intensification of learning through the use of new pedagogical technologies and the introduction of new academic subjects contributes to the increase of informational, emotional and mental stress, as a result of which health , a decrease in creative, intellectual and physical activity. , decrease in efficiency of introduced innovations.

The analysis of the conducted psychological-pedagogical research allows us to conclude that the problem of formation and development of the subject of activity in the conditions of innovative processes in the educational system is very urgent and is being studied in various psychological-pedagogical directions. There are no effective methods of analyzing innovation processes, not only in the professional, but also in the personal sphere. However, this problem is not over yet, each new stage of development of the modern educational space requires a new, deeper understanding of this problem and the justification of new approaches to its solution. One of these areas is the role and importance of the leader in the management of innovation processes.[4]

Modern social processes are extremely fast and the leader requires constant self-education, reflective introspection, formation of social, personal and innovative competencies. The effective innovative activity of the leader in the educational system is an important factor driving the dynamics of educational technologies, a guarantee of non-standard solutions that determine the

investment character of investments in an autonomous educational institution, and the satisfaction of educational subjects. indicator of stability of process and creative teams.

The study of innovative processes in education is mainly focused on teachers, pedagogical staff, which ignores the management segment of the work of educational institutions. In addition, modern development processes determine the dynamism and uncertainty of the size, content and character of innovation processes in educational institutions, therefore, the activities of the leader in the innovation system require specific research, understanding and generalization. The constant change of the content of management activities, the mobility of organizational structures that ensure the stimulation of innovative processes in the educational system require special innovative skills, abilities and qualities from the head of the educational institution [5]

Based on the theoretical analysis of local and foreign literature on management education, management sociology and psychology, general pedagogy, vocational education, innovative management competence implies the following competencies: tendency to innovation or discoveries; the ability to see new elements when set relatively; the ability to propose a radically new solution to a problem; readiness for leadership work; the ability to make reasonable social and management decisions and actions in social and educational institutions. Innovative and management competence directs the management subject to reflective experience to see the material for innovative changes in the future, but does not stop there. The subject is in a state of arbitrary creative search, proposing new solutions, tools and technologies for changing objects until the existing approaches - educational-technological, social-management, implementation, reflective-analysis, etc. are exhausted. tends to do. Since such decisions are related to the specific characteristics of the changed object, according to the nature of its directed change, it is possible to assess the level of innovation and management skills of the leading entity to a certain extent.[6] Innovative and management competence is considered by us (see Figure 1) on the basis of two qualitative formations - the ability and readiness of the leader to carry out activities on the management of innovative processes in the open education system. One of the structural quality forms of innovation and management competence - at the center of the ability, we put forward a complex, multi-functional structure: innovation capacity. The innovative potential of a leader is a changer at different levels of social and educational interaction (subject-subject and subject-object) necessary for the implementation of effective management and innovative activity of a person, the ability to perform reflective, innovative activity is understood. The leader's innovative potential is an important psychological factor, it is an inalienable property of a person and determines his attitude to innovation. Its components: the practicality and creativity of thinking, the need for self-expression and success, organizational skills, and self-confidence. Traditionally, problems of innovative potential have been developed by systems theory within the framework of economic concepts of scientific and technical development. Recently, due to its versatility, it has gone beyond the scope of economics itself and finds its effective application in many areas of scientific knowledge.

In recent years, more and more attention has been paid to the innovative potential of the head of the educational institution. The analysis of foreign literature devoted to the problems of innovation showed that the category "innovative potential of a person" was mentioned in the monograph "Innovation: the basis of cultural changes" published by the American sociologist H. Barnett in the early 1950s. in 1953.

In modern conditions, the rapidly changing world demands different management methods from the head of educational institutions. The leader who can respond to new changes the fastest, who can perceive and reflect on changes in education and society, and who can implement what he plans, is the leader who wins. practical use of their innovative capabilities. The innovative potential of the leader actually provides the ability to effectively manage innovative processes in the educational institution. Experience shows that a major reorganization is only possible if the leader can build a team of like-minded people, who can politely and decisively confront the opponents of innovation.

Currently, there is a disparity between the availability of innovative opportunities and their practical implementation in local education. Leaders of educational institutions (higher, secondary, special) rarely have high innovative potential, but there are also few who can use it effectively. The problem of determining the personal qualities of people with high and low innovative potential, the age characteristics of its development, has not been solved. Innovative problems are mainly developed within the framework of the descriptive paradigm, and in this regard, the task of determining the explanatory status of psychological problems of changes in various etymologies is undoubtedly relevant. The problem is related to the lack of comprehensive research, methodological developments and conceptual approaches to evaluate the innovative potential and the effectiveness of its use. Considering these reasons, it is an urgent task to study the innovative potential of the leader.

It is appropriate to reveal the essence of the concept of "innovative potential" by defining its structural categories. The concept of "potential" comes from the Latin word "potentia", which means power, strength, opportunity, ability that exists in a hidden form and can manifest itself under certain conditions. In physics, the concept of "potential" describes the magnitude of potential energy at a certain point in space. In this case, the potential energy is the internal energy reserve depending on the position of the body or the interaction energy determined by the mutual location of the system bodies in space. In a broader sense, potential is a set of existing factors that can be used and acted upon to achieve a specific goal and result. Also, potential can be obvious and hidden, used or unused.

Taking into account the above, the category of "innovative potential" can be interpreted as the ability of the system to transform the actual order of things into a new state in order to satisfy existing or newly emerging needs (innovator subject). At the same time, the effective use of innovative potential allows to move from a hidden possibility to a concrete reality, that is, from one state to another (from traditional to new). Therefore, innovative potential is a characteristic of the system's ability to change, improve and develop. To date, there are few studies that determine the innovative potential of a person and, in particular, the personality of a leader in the educational system. The general structure of the individual's innovative potential is considered taking into account the motivational (primarily success motivation), emotional and volitional spheres, cognitive processes (variety of thinking, level of persistence of thought processes, etc.) working models.), individual characteristics of the subject of activity (creativity, internality in decision-making).

M. V. Chigrinova [5], who studied the innovative potential of an effective and ineffective leader using Kelly's repertoire networks, concluded that one of the components of the innovative potential is the cognitive sphere of the individual, and in particular, the management system. a person's subjective opinions about the essence of innovative activity and the psychological

characteristics of the participant in the introduction of innovations. Through this reference system, which has an independent ontological status, the process of evaluating the available and necessary internal and external means of activity is carried out, which ensures a certain level of innovative potential of the individual. M. V. Chigrinova determined that the innovative potential is high if the following content is strengthened in the individual concept of a person: the perception of a person's role in interacting with the world as an active, proactive participation in innovative activities; comprehensive ideas about a creative approach to professional activity; communicative ability; the idea of a creative, active attitude to reality as an important value in activity.

V. B. Yakovenko, one of the modern researchers of innovation processes, introduced the concept of "operational innovative energy potential of a person" and connects it with the influence of the intensity of a person's innovative perception, which, in turn, is largely influenced by age. Thus, there are different concepts of innovation potential. The above studies do not reveal its entire essence, but only consider some of its parts. In this regard, approaches to determining the composition of innovative potential differ. An important quality education of innovative and management competence is the leader's personal readiness to manage innovative processes in an educational institution. By the preparation of the leader, we understand the individual psychological orientation, autonomy, initiative for voluntary activities, mobilization of abilities for innovative activities and appropriate abilities, effective actions.

Conclusion. The process of realizing a person's innovative potential and personal preparation of a leader can be expressed as a unity of three potential opportunities that are updated in the process of interaction to perceive new information, adequately evaluate a new phenomenon and change it. and readiness for effective innovative activity. The characteristics of this interaction determine the ratio of leadership types to the actualization of innovative opportunities and can be the basis for determining the types of leaders and their management styles. Assessment of the quality of achieving the target innovative function and management competence is achieved by determining the preference for one or another type and method of management (according to the principle of efficiency) in a specific problem situation.

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